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TITLE: HUMANITARIAN CORRIDORS: GUIDELINES FOR IMPLEMENTATION OF
THE INTEGRATION PATHWAYS

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DISCLAIMER

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FOREWORD

The formation of an effective migration and asylum policy is one of the great challenges that the European Union is facing.

The current Common European Asylum System has revealed its shortcomings if we look at the refugee crisis that occurred in 2015 and 2016 in Europe. Situations such as the management of external borders, the externalisation of borders with the EU – Turkey Agreement or the application, for the first time, of Art. 78.3 of the Treaty on the Functioning of the European Union, are issues that have highlighted the need to undertake a reform of the system.

In this sense, the European Union has recently worked on the so-called New Pact on Migration and Asylum, which aims to carry out a profound review of the current system. Essentially, among other things, the aim is to achieve a more supportive system, where the burdens can be equitably distributed to the different Member States, in order not to penalise Member States with an external border.

However, despite the ambitious reform proposal represented by the New Pact, there is no legally binding provision on private sponsorship systems for refugees or specific models, such as Humanitarian Corridors. The only non-binding documentary reference that can refer to private sponsorship schemes is Recommendation 2020/1364 on legal pathways to protection in the EU: promoting resettlement, humanitarian admission and other complementary pathways.

In recitals 26 and 28 it is stated as follows:

26:

“Several Member States have implemented community sponsorship schemes, which can underpin resettlement, humanitarian admission and other complementary pathways. In all cases, private sponsors, groups of private individuals or non-profit organisations can play a structured role in welcoming and integrating those in need of international protection”.

28:

“Other forms of community sponsorship beyond resettlement, which can serve as a model, include what some Member States and private organisations refer to as ‘humanitarian corridors’, namely the community sponsorship model currently implemented by faith-based organisations in Italy, France and Belgium in cooperation with the respective national governments. Under this model, private sponsors are involved in all stages of the admission process, from identifying those in need of international protection to transferring them to the Member State concerned. They also take charge of reception and integration efforts and bear the related costs”.

Finally, point 14 of the Recommendation indicates that the European Commission invites Member States to establish or expand private sponsorship programs, where groups of individuals or NGOs participate.

It is noted, therefore, that there is currently no binding legal instrument to oblige Member States to develop private sponsorship programs. Our consideration consists of assessing that private

sponsorship programs, such as humanitarian corridors, or other types (community sponsorship – United Kingdom or Portugal) are a necessary complement to the Common European Asylum System and to other practices such as resettlement or humanitarian admission.

In the case of the “Humanitarian Corridors”, which are based on the Civil Society initiative, it may be worth noting that they can be also functional to the introduction of certain ambitious proposals of reform within the framework of asylum and immigration policies, such as the introduction (or re-introduction) of the legal instrument of “Sponsorship” in further Member States.

Created in Italy as a means to provide answers to the needs of the thousands of refugees who are fleeing situations of war and poverty and seeking shelter in bordering countries or in Europe, the Humanitarian Corridors are a particularly significant and original case of sponsorship for people who are potentially entitled to international protection and who are in vulnerable conditions (as provided for by European Directive 2013/33 of 26 June 2013)¹.

Humanitarian Corridors, which were implemented for the first time from Lebanon to Italy in favour of Syrian refugees fleeing the civil war which broke out in Syria in 2011, have proven, over the years, to be an effective tool for the integration of refugees in Europe: since 2016, over 6,500 people have been welcomed and found integration, for the most part in Italy, France and Belgium.

The “welcoming and integration model” established by the Humanitarian Corridors has the potential to be replicated in other countries or local contexts or by further Sponsors. These Guidelines are therefore intended to serve as a useful support tool for actual or potential promoters or sponsors, and for the members of civil society in different European countries who wish to be engaged in implementation of the model.

¹ Chapter IV - Provisions for vulnerable persons, Article 21: “...vulnerable persons such as minors, unaccompanied minors, disabled people, elderly people, pregnant women, single parents with minor children, victims of human trafficking, persons with serious illnesses, persons with mental disorders and persons who have been subjected to torture, rape or other serious forms of psychological, physical or sexual violence, such as victims of female genital mutilation”.

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Introduction

1

Acronyms and Abbreviations

CSOs

Civil Society Organisations

EU

European Union

HC

Humanitarian Corridors

IO

International Organisations

IOM

International Organisation for Migration

MoU

Memorandum of Understanding

MS

Member States

NGOs

Non-governmental organisations

PEP

Protected Entry Procedures

PSS

Private Sponsorship Scheme

UNHCR

United Nations High Commissioner for Refugees

Why these Guidelines

This “HUMANITARIAN CORRIDORS: GUIDELINES FOR IMPLEMENTATION OF THE INTEGRATION PATHWAYS” has been developed within the framework of the “Humanitarian Corridors Integration pathways: fostering better integration opportunities for people in need of protection through strengthened private sponsorship schemes” – HUMCORE project funded by AMIF (Asylum, Migration and Integration Fund) of the European Union - AMIF - 2020 – AG.

The project began in December 2021 and is coordinated by the Italian association COMMUNITY OF S. EGIDIO ACAP – APS, in partnership with: COMUNITA PAPA GIOVANNI XXIII and CONSIGLIO NAZIONALE DELLE RICERCHE, Italy; SOCIETA DANTE ALIGHIERI, Poland; SOCIAL RESEARCH AND POLICY INSTITUTE, Bulgaria; SANT’EGIDIO BXL EUROPE, Belgium; FORSKINGSCENTRUM FOR EUROPEISK FLERSPRAKIGHET OPPET BOLAG, Finland; ASSOCIACION COMMUNAUTE SANT'EGIDIO FRANCE, France; SODERTORNS HOGSKOLA, Sweden; ISTITUTO POLITECNICO DE BRAGANCA, Portugal; FUNDACION BLANQUERNA, Spain.

The “HUMCORE” project is aimed at fostering integration of third-country nationals in need of protection, thanks to actions aimed at improving the procedures and practices of the Humanitarian Corridors (HC), a Private Sponsorship Scheme operating since 2016. By involving eight EU countries and combining the review analysis of the aspects of HC specifically linked to integration with capacity-building activities addressed at the sponsors, HUMCORE aimed to achieve an enhanced Scheme offering better integration.

To this end, the project gave support to 1,000 beneficiaries coming from non-EU countries in the achievement of autonomy and integration in EU countries (and notably, France and Italy). The project provided full integration pathways to 200 out of the 1,000 beneficiaries.

The Guidelines are, therefore, the outcome of the results achieved and of the assessments expressed following implementation of the two work phases. Their objective is to provide an operational reference on setting up Humanitarian Corridors (and integration pathways), illustrating the procedures for the implementation of the HC integration model, including:

- How to set up the framework for implementation of the HCs, including selection of the Sponsors
- How to implement integration pathways effectively, through the different phases from pre-departure to post-arrival, including procedures and lessons learnt.

Further information on the “HUMCORE” project may be found on the website: www.humcore.org.

To Whom the Guidelines are addressed

The Guidelines are for CSOs, Promoters” or “Sponsors” of the Humanitarian Corridors and Policy-Makers in the field of immigration and the right to asylum at EU and national level.

The Guidelines focus on how to implement the integration pathways effectively within the framework of the Humanitarian Corridors, but are also useful for public and private actors (Authorities, CSOs, NGOs) operating or intending to operate within the framework of Private Partner Schemes (PPS) or in the field of management of migration flows, relocation and resettlement².

Structure of the Guidelines

The Guidelines comprise four main sections, as described in Chapter 4, organised by following the main implementation phases set up for implementation of the Humanitarian Corridors:

- ⇒ Setting up the framework,
- ⇒ Pre-departure activities,
- ⇒ Arrival and Welcoming,
- ⇒ Post-arrival and Integration.

Each section contains sub-sections describing in detail the operational procedures and presenting examples, tips and tools.

All the sections and sub-sections are designed specifically to highlight the existing link between the main implementation phases and the way in which they contribute to the final aim of integration of the beneficiaries into the EU countries.

² “The “humanitarian corridors” [provide for] the possibility that their beneficiaries are not among those for whom the UNHCR has ordered international protection, differing in the sense that they do not presuppose, although do not exclude, the temporary nature of their stay, but rather aim at the best possible social inclusion in a scenario which in the short term should allow, partly as a result of national policies to stop immigration for work purposes, the possibility of greater stabilisation of those who come to the European Union for reasons of asylum”.

[...] “The difference between “humanitarian corridors” and the European framework for resettlement also concerns a second aspect, since it is the firm conviction of the promoters of the “humanitarian corridors” that they do not want to include them in the number of resettlements promoted by the European Union for individual Member States. In short, it is necessary to avoid the drive for a greater commitment to solidarity of European civil societies being offset, thus resulting in a zero-sum situation, by the commitments that individual countries will need to take on with regards to the European Union and the UNHCR.” P. Morozzo della Rocca, I due Protocolli d’Intesa sui “Corridoi Umanitari” tra alcuni enti di ispirazione religiosa e il governo ed il loro possibile impatto sulle politiche di asilo e immigrazione. (The two Memoranda of Understanding on the “Humanitarian Corridors” between several religious bodies and the government and their possible impact on asylum and immigration policies). Diritto, Immigrazione e Cittadinanza - File no. 1, 2017

HUMANITARIAN CORRIDORS: *do you know this practice?*

2

Why Humanitarian Corridors

Humanitarian Corridors aim to achieve the following general objectives:

- avoid the death of migrants who try to reach Europe by sea;
- enable people in a vulnerable situation (single women, children, sick/disabled people, elderly people, etc.) to access the international protection system through safe and legal entry into Europe;
- fight the exploitation by traffickers and trafficking in human beings;
- test a good practice which can then be replicated in other European contexts, as it is based on European legislation;
- offer a significant trial regarding the possibility of introducing/reintroducing/boosting the Sponsorship instrument in the legislative-operational contexts of the Member States, also on the basis of the most recent experiences and of those that have already been in place for a long time in various countries on other continents (such as, for example, Canada and the United States).

The guidelines and procedures envisaged for the implementation of the Humanitarian Corridors, reported below, have been prepared and tested to facilitate the achievement of the aforementioned main objectives, including in view of the replicability of the model in other contexts and in further European countries.

For whom? Beneficiaries

The “potential beneficiaries” of the Humanitarian Corridors are:

- people in the conditions described in European Directive 2013/33 of 26 June 2013 and in vulnerable conditions due to age, sex, state of health (e.g. families with children, single mothers with children, disabled people, people with serious illnesses, victims of trafficking, torture, violence);
- people falling within the cases provided for by Article 3 of the Memorandum of Understanding (or Project Protocol), which remains substantially unchanged regardless of the geographical areas of applicability of the different Humanitarian Corridors in force up to now, without preclusion or discrimination in relation to religious or social groups or personal characteristics;
- people recognised by the UNHCR as prima facie refugees under the 1951 Geneva Convention and its 1967 Protocol;
- people facing serious threats to their life or freedom due to armed conflict, endemic violence or systematic violations of human rights;
- people with relatives in the country of resettlement.

By whom?

Promotors (or Coordinators)

The organisations (CSOs, NGOs) promoting the Humanitarian Corridors, signatory parties of the Memoranda of Understanding with the National Authorities. They are also the “Main Sponsors” or the “Organisational Sponsors”. They can be considered as the “initial” sponsors, since they are often responsible for guiding sponsors and co-sponsors through the sponsorship process and may provide a safety net if the individual sponsorship falls through. They identify and select the beneficiaries in the countries of departure and select the “Sponsors” in charge of the welcoming and the integration pathways in EU countries.

Sponsors

The “Sponsor” is either an organisation or an individual, part of the network of civil society organisations that initially negotiated the protocol or memorandum of understanding with National Authorities. Sponsors often operate together with individuals (volunteers, private citizens or – extended - family members) to provide support to beneficiaries.

Co-sponsors

They are either an organisation or an individual, acting at local level, who may help the Promotors or the Sponsors in providing support to beneficiaries.

The challenges to which the Humanitarian Corridors respond

CHALLENGES	RESPONSE
<p>1. Prevent deaths at sea</p> <p>SAFE ENTRY</p>	<p>Identification of the Beneficiaries in the countries of departure (transit countries): based on beneficiaries' vulnerability and living conditions, livelihood opportunities, access to education and level of protection.</p> <p>Pre-departure activities (in non-EU countries): orientation of the beneficiaries; preparation of the trips, the welcoming and integration pathways.</p>
<p>2. Fight human trafficking</p> <p>LEGAL ENTRY</p>	<p>Signature of memoranda or protocols establishing the operational framework for the implementation of the Humanitarian Corridors in the country and the responsibilities of the promoters/sponsors (and government): the signees are responsible for the overall HC scheme and the integration of the beneficiaries.</p> <p>Legal entry and status granted upon arrival: Visa for Limited Territorial Validity on humanitarian grounds (LTV C visa)³. Application for international protection is required upon arrival⁴. Associated rights are the same as for holders of an international protection status.</p>
<p>3. Sustainable reception of refugees</p> <p>SPONSORSHIP</p>	<p>Welcoming at local level: Sponsors provide accommodation and support, including assistance in the process of granting legal protection and related rights (healthcare, education, etc.)</p>
<p>4. Effective inclusion</p> <p>INTEGRATION</p>	<p>Integration pathways: Sponsors provide support in the process of social inclusion, including access to work and housing. The duration of the pathways to achieve autonomy ranges from 12 to 15 months (with some exceptions, depending on the difficulties and specific vulnerabilities)</p> <p>Monitoring: the HCs Scheme is monitored by the Promoters; the Integration Pathways are monitored by the Promoters in association with the Sponsors.</p>

³ As per Article 25 of the Visa Code Regulation (Regulation 810/2009).

⁴ Applicants must apply for asylum within 3 months.

The overall pathway for the implementation of the Humanitarian Corridors is presented in Fig. 1.1

Fig. 1.1 - General pathway for implementation of the Humanitarian Corridors

**HUMANITARIAN CORRIDORS: *Guidelines
on Integration Pathways***

0. SETTING UP THE FRAMEWORK

The following set of Guidelines apply to:

- possible signees of the Agreement on adoption of the Humanitarian Corridors (**National Authorities and Promoters**):

01. Check National legislation

- ➔ **01.1: Investigate what is the best tool to support sponsored beneficiaries.** The Humanitarian Corridors scheme is in line with the EU legal framework and none of the EU Member States which have set up this scheme (or other forms of PPS) to date have amended their national legislation.
- ➔ **01.2: Apply the flexibility allowed by the Humanitarian Corridors (as private sponsorship schemes do) when designing your scheme at national and local levels,** to tailor it to your institutional framework, to assess the refugee or migrant population and the interest of communities when considering their contribution to operation of the Humanitarian Corridors scheme.

02. Preparing the Memorandum of Understanding (MoU)

- **02.1: The MoU is the main agreement establishing the Humanitarian Corridors.** Design a memorandum of understanding (or agreement) containing only the essential and qualifying elements for implementation of the Humanitarian Corridors, not the operational details: methods and timing of entries; countries of origin and number of beneficiaries; distribution of obligations among the signees; tasks and responsibilities of each of the parties in the different phases of implementation and management; general methods and duration of the integration pathways; monitoring system. This way, it will be easier to identify what the parties have agreed upon and subsequently incorporate any adaptations within the scope of the operational procedures.

ANNEX 1: EXAMPLE OF MoU

03. Identifying the Sponsors

- **03.1: Exploit the Promoters' network to identify Sponsors at local level:** the initial “organisational” sponsors are part of the network of civil society organisations that initially negotiated the protocol or memorandum of understanding with national authorities. ‘Organisational’ sponsors often operate together with individuals (volunteers, private citizens or (extended) family members) to provide support to beneficiaries. Starting with potential “organisational sponsors” already on the network makes the sponsorship process smoother. Furthermore, they may provide a safety net if the individual sponsorship falls through. The involvement of individual sponsors relies on membership (as a volunteer, for example) of one of the civil society organisations implementing the programme, or on a ‘sponsoring group’ (e.g., of up to 10 volunteers) who prepare a ‘project’ to welcome selected families. The reception system of the Humanitarian Corridors involves grassroots associations, groups of friends, parishes, churches, single families, formal and informal networks of people, etc. A very large number of volunteer operators is actively involved in the different phases and activities of the beneficiaries’ integration pathways.

*The Story of **Mattia**: from a single family to a welcoming community*

My name is Mattia, and I come from the Marche region in Italy. I represent a community of families who were not afraid to open their doors and ultimately found themselves with many new relatives, coming from afar, who are no longer strangers today. For my family, everything began in 2018 when my father-in-law, Lamberto, the leader of a group of volunteers, left us the legacy of accompanying a Syrian family, who arrived with one of the first humanitarian corridors: father, mother, and two young children, fleeing from the bombs and destruction in Homs. "Think about it, your children, Bianca Maria and Francesco, will have the opportunity to interact with children from another culture!" Lamberto proudly told us the day after their arrival in Italy. "You lost a father, but you gained two brothers," Anton and Nadine told us at Lamberto's funeral, just forty days after their arrival. So, two more brothers, the discovery of the Community of Sant'Egidio, and a small revolution beginning in the Marche, in the small town of Castelfidardo, with other extraordinary families and fellow travellers: Dariana, Paolo, Alessandro, and Barbara, to name just a few. Together, we organised everything: some took care of the school for Mousa and Yana, some handled medical visits, others documents, house hunting, and work, which was not lacking here.

Of course, as happens in all families, there were some misunderstandings, especially at the beginning, due not only to cultural differences but above all to deep inner wounds and to the difficulty of regaining trust in others: "In war, you no longer know who you can trust," they repeated to us several times. Only now, after a war, in Ukraine, that threatens peace in Europe, have I managed to grasp the true meaning of those words. Yes, because building bridges also means questioning oneself. Nothing happens by chance. In the midst of the lockdown, Providence wanted our experience to meet that of new friends from the Marche, who in Macerata and Civitanova, wanted to repeat our experience. So, like a positive contagion, from that first corridor, two more were born. That's why today ours is no longer just a simple experience. We are convinced that it is much more: humanitarian corridors are a safe way to save human lives and are a great gift for our Europe, often aged and resigned. Our hope is to see this model extended to the entire continent. We are here to testify to this, and I believe that my words also apply to all those, many, who have hosted in Italy and in Europe: from hospitality and integration, a culturally and humanly enriched society can emerge. A changed world.

04. Informing and Training the Sponsors

- ➔ **04.1: Inform and train the Sponsors:** private sponsors will form reception networks in specific areas (city, suburb, village, etc.). HCs adopt the so-called "widespread reception model", meaning that the beneficiaries are received in different social and geographical environments: in big cities or small villages, in different regions, in single apartments or in communities, in religious premises or in houses for rent, etc. According to this model, beneficiaries do not represent a separate group asked to coexist with the rest of society, but they are scattered across the territory and travel along their own personal

integration pathway, based on their own characteristics, plans and attitudes. Sponsors are informed and trained at different times. When sponsors are still potential and interested in entering the programme, the training activities are intended to: inform them about the crucial issues of an integration pathways; suggest how to organise a reception group capable of dealing with crucial issues; in practice, it means that each group must have a specific responsibility for the crucial tasks (housing, school etc.); ask the groups to name a coordinator and to set up a system of periodic internal meetings (a weekly basis would be ideal); reassure the sponsors on the promoter's continuous support, especially if difficulties emerge during reception; evaluate the group's capacity to create and fund an integration pathway and decide together whether and how to go ahead. Information and training meetings are then provided when the sponsors have been involved in reception of the beneficiaries.

05. Monitoring the Scheme

- ➔ **05.1: Create a clear (not excessive or oversized) coordination mechanism between the CSOs (promoters) and national authorities (e.g., Ministries)** who are parties to the MoU or protocol, and organise regular meetings to discuss and facilitate issues encountered during implementation of the HC scheme.
- ➔ **05.2: Include peer support as an element of the monitoring system** to foster supportive relationships between stakeholders involved in carrying out the HC program and sponsorship activities, share best practices, potential challenges and experiences among the groups that work most closely with sponsors and beneficiaries. Activities like coordination meetings, visits or mentoring can create opportunities to build these relationships.
- ➔ **05.3: Envisage specific support measures to benefit sponsors and civil society:** training or training materials (e.g. handbooks, webinars, videos) that could be used directly by sponsors or by those currently providing training to sponsors (e.g. CSOs already in the network or newcomers). Such materials should focus on crucial aspects of HCs and/or related integration pathways that are common across Member States, local environments or beneficiaries, such as how to manage cultural differences, information on beneficiaries' countries of origin, or how to avoid dependency and support beneficiaries in transitioning at the end of an integration pathway.
- ➔ **05.4: Set up and implement an online database** of information and resources on beneficiaries and integration pathways, managed by the promoter/coordinator and shared with the sponsors who work closely with the beneficiaries.

- ➔ **05.5: Set up and implement a consistent system of indicators** tailored to monitor and evaluate the “crucial issues” of the integration pathways, such as: attendance of language courses (and intermediate results); school attendance for minors (and intermediate results); capacity to autonomously manage a house/household; capacity to have social relations; acquisition of documents and recognition of refugee status; attendance of vocational or upskill training; active involvement in seeking employment (and capacity to deal with related issues) and outcomes; progressive financial independence (and capacity to deal with related issues) and achievement of financial independence.

1. PREPARING FOR INTEGRATION: PRE-DEPARTURE

The following Guidelines apply to:

- *Promoters and Members of the HC networks (CSOs, sponsors, stakeholders) in non-EU countries of departure and in EU destination countries.*

1.1 PREPARING BENEFICIARIES

- ➔ **1.1.1: Set up and implement the referral verification system:** Regardless of the nature and obligations of the promoters/sponsors involved in referrals of potential beneficiaries, design and implement a multi-level and double-check verification system to check the reports collected from stakeholders (UNHCR, IOM, NGOs, associations, family members, etc.) in the countries of origin: three or even more levels of in-depth analysis before acceptance of a formal request of admission to the Humanitarian Corridors are strongly recommended. This system should be detailed through operational guidelines.
- ➔ **1.1.2: Set up and implement a comprehensive system (and related procedures) of assessment in situ of the requests for admission** based on direct contacts with the potential beneficiaries (preferably in the home/place of residence or temporary residence of the people concerned). At least three interviews should be envisaged, intended to establish the existence of the eligibility criteria (e.g., vulnerability) and the planned integration of the beneficiaries in the EU country of destination. As a result of

the interviews, the following information should be collected: composition of the family and circle of relatives; cultural background and education; personal history and events which led the person and/or the family to leave their country; reasons for their application for international protection; verification of the personal documentation in their possession. Particular attention should be paid to evaluating the motivational aspects which induce the interviewees to ask for international protection and to be included in the project. The truthfulness of the personal/family history described by the potential beneficiaries should be carefully analysed and evaluated through various verification sources: databases, information provided by other people in the field, region, city, etc.

- **1.1.3 Provide tailored, fine-tuned information and cultural orientation to beneficiaries in the perspective of integration in the EU.** A set of pre-departure activities should be provided to beneficiaries, which comprise: a. information sessions about the situation that they will find in Europe/the destination country. One of the most important elements for the success of integration relies on the correctness of the expectations of the beneficiaries, who must be as aware as possible of the conditions and situations they will encounter in Europe, from every point of view (from climate to social habits, from legal system to school obligations, from the role of private sponsors to their own responsibilities during the program, etc.); b. information sessions on the rules and regulations with which the beneficiaries will have to comply in the EU and the commitments necessary to their integration: language learning for all, school attendance for minors, active job search, progressive financial independence, etc. It is crucial that, before leaving, beneficiaries internalise the importance of these tasks and feel fully responsible for their accomplishment; c. basic language training to enable beneficiaries to communicate in an elementary way with sponsors from the very beginning of the integration pathway (even if intercultural mediators will remain at full disposal as long as needed).

1.2 MATCHING BENEFICIARIES/SPONSORS

- **1.2.1 List and implement “matching criteria”, but be open-minded in matching specific beneficiaries to sponsors at local level.** A proper match is the key element of the integration pathways, since the daily life of beneficiaries will take place in close contact with sponsors. A harmonious relationship between the two sides is the best guarantee of success. Sponsors have to build a strong human relation with beneficiaries, based essentially on mutual trust. In the beneficiaries’ eyes, the sponsor has to be a best friend, someone to rely on, a competent support in solving issues and an authoritative voice whose suggestions and indications deserve to be followed. The use of intercultural mediation is strongly recommended to facilitate the relationships between sponsors and beneficiaries. Equally, sponsors must manage the integration process in full respect for the beneficiaries’ sensitivity, feelings, expectations and possible moments of crisis. Promoters will assist and support both the sponsors and the beneficiaries when

necessary. A good match clearly relies on the quality and effectiveness of the pre-departure activities addressed to sponsors and to beneficiaries. The conditions and expectations of specific beneficiaries have to “match” with the capabilities and the skills of a given reception group, also taking into account the characteristics of the environment (socio-economic situation, urbanisation, climate etc). It is essential for the promoter to have full knowledge of all elements of the integration pathway: beneficiaries, sponsors and outside factors.

BOX 1 – MAIN MATCHING CRITERIA

CRITERIA

-
- A. *Type of beneficiaries:*
- ✓ **families with children,**
 - ✓ **couples,**
 - ✓ **single young people,**
 - ✓ **lonely men/women with children,**
 - ✓ **sick,**
 - ✓ **others.**
- B. *Socio-economic condition of the area where a reception group is based:*
- ✓ **big city or small village,**
 - ✓ **presence of commercial/industrial/agricultural activities,**
 - ✓ **presence of facilities (e.g., proximity to specialised hospitals or to specific schools),**
 - ✓ **job opportunities,**
 - ✓ **presence of associations of volunteers or entities involved in supporting vulnerable people,**
 - ✓ **others.**
- C. *Appropriate housing for every family group/person, based on specific conditions e.g., reduced mobility):*
- ✓ **Houses or apartments or rooms suitable and accessible for different types of beneficiaries**
- D. *specific features of the reception groups, specific points of strength and capabilities.*
-

1.3 PREPARING SPONSORS AND CO-SPONSORS

- ➔ **1.3.1 Provide information and assistance to sponsors at local level before departure of the beneficiaries from the transit countries.** Information meetings and training are provided by the promoter after having matched the sponsor with an identified beneficiary (individual or group or family). The purpose of meetings and training is to: provide the sponsors with detailed information and indications on their specific tasks and financial commitments; provide the sponsors and local groups with detailed information on the people/family who are going to arrive; set up a system of periodic

meetings between the sponsor, the local group and the promoter, as well as between the sponsor, the group and the beneficiaries (internal meetings will continue); agree on the financial and/or organisational support needed by the sponsor and provided by the promoter; organise the first meeting between beneficiaries and “their own” sponsors on arrival at the airport.

- ➔ **1.3.2 Attribute to the sponsors (supported by the promoters) the responsibility for involvement of local communities, associations, facilities at local level**, clearly linking the welcoming phase with the subsequent integration pathways. To do so, beneficiaries’ needs should be assessed, stakeholders identified and strategies designed in advance, having regard to the following main topics: availability of schools, housing, language training, and other services; specific services for the sick or vulnerable. Welcoming strategy design should clearly include definition of any understandings or agreements with stakeholders on these topics (e.g., framework agreement signed with language schools at local level) and related practical answers to specific needs (e.g., contacts/appointments made with healthcare facilities/hospitals for medical care). This strategy should be defined prior to arrival of the beneficiaries and adjusted (if necessary) during the reception period.

BOX 2: CAPACITY BUILDING AND PEER-LEARNING FOR SPONSORS AND CO-SPONSORS

Help relationship among sponsor groups and HC beneficiaries.

Methods

Sessions (in-presence and online)

CAPACITY BUILDING

Participants

Promoters, Sponsors and Co-Sponsors

Main Contents

The relationship between the reception group and the final beneficiaries is a pivotal element of the HC model, and definitely the most difficult to codify or plan in advance. The two parties to this relationship meet for the first time on the day of arrival, even if they have both received information in advance about the other. It is fundamental that a mutual trust immediately emerges between them and is progressively reinforced. Since this is a relationship between individuals, psychology and cultural mediation are the most useful tools to improve the quality of the relationship itself. Some points are discussed among participants, under the coordination of experts: *What exactly does it mean to be a refugee? How do you deal with trauma? What does displacement mean for refugees? “Gratitude”: what does it mean and how to deal with this principle? What can operators expect from refugees? What can and can’t we do for them?*

How to deal with the practical tasks of a welcoming and integration pathway

Methods

Sessions (in-presence and online)

Participants

**PEER
LEARNING**

Promoters, Sponsors and Co-Sponsors, Experienced Sponsors

Main Contents

Presentation and discussion of practical tasks and issues of the welcoming and integration pathways: strengthening the capacity of the local sponsors. The experienced group presents experiences acquired from past receptions. They provide elements to address doubts and issues raised by sponsors in preparation for the reception of incoming refugees, such as: *how to deal with first accommodation and how to ensure further support for housing; how to deal with language learning, education and training; refugees' habits and how to deal with daily life needs; how to support beneficiaries in the process of granting legal status and access services; how to provide support in finding employment.*

How to broaden and strengthen local support networks

Methods

Sessions (in-presence and online)

**PEER
LEARNING**

Participants

Promoters, Sponsors and Co-Sponsors, Experienced Sponsors

Main Contents

Exchange of experiences and information on how to broaden and strengthen support networks at local level. The main topics under discussion are: how to reach out both to the general public (as individuals and families are among the network members) and the members of civil society? How to involve them in supporting refugees?

1.4 PREPARING FOR DEPARTURE (SAFE AND LEGAL ENTRY)

- ➔ **1.4.1 Attribute to the Promoters the main responsibility for organising the departure of the beneficiaries from the transit countries**, which comprises of the main phases highlighted in picture 1.2.
- ➔ **1.4.2 Prepare individual/family files for each beneficiary.** A preliminary list containing data and information on each beneficiary selected for departure is prepared. The list contains the following information: the code assigned to each person by the UNHCR, or a code assigned to the family, or a food card number; a telephone number. A picture of each person, a photo of the family and the history of each family member are provided and stored. The list is then sent to the relevant authorities in the transit country concerned, accompanied by a map of family ties/relationships between beneficiaries (family booklets). The “proofs of registration”⁵ are collected. Identity documents are

⁵ The registration of refugees aims to protect and assist refugees waiting to implement durable solutions. The registration of refugees and asylum seekers is an essential tool for their protection from eventualities such as repression, arrest and arbitrary detention. It also provides access to the fundamental rights, services and assistance they need. The registration of minors guarantees family unity and, in the case of children separated from the family, helps in their

translated into English. Correspondence between the data and the information on the list drawn up by the relevant authorities (e.g.: UNHCR) and those on the list is carefully verified to avoid discrepancies. In the cases provided for by the regulations in force, the list of beneficiaries is also sent to the Immigration Office (or to other relevant authorities). For example, in the case of Ethiopia, the list is sent to the ARRA and to the Ministry of the Interior and ARRA requests, for each beneficiary, the following documents: an application form completed and signed by the beneficiary to be deposited at the Immigration Office; biometric data; telephone number and address; an identification photograph.

- ➔ **1.4.3 Manage the flow of information necessary for conducting the security checks related to the intended beneficiaries before departure.** Upon submission of the appropriate requests, the competent authorities issue travel documents for the beneficiaries. Security screenings involve, at this stage, checking congruence of the data of each beneficiary (e.g. fingerprints). Based on information included in the travel documents, the relevant authorities in the country of destination may request further information on beneficiaries. For example, in the case of Italy, the Ministry of the Interior requests that an application form for each beneficiary be provided, containing the following documentation and information: identity document; indication of the city of destination. Once the final list of beneficiaries is ready and approved, it is sent to the operating airline and to the police in the destination country. The following information is transmitted as well: composition of the families; address of residence of the beneficiaries; personal data and telephone number of the person responsible for their reception.
- ➔ **1.4.4 Organise pre-departure medical checks for beneficiaries.** Medical checks, which vary based on personal conditions, are performed one week before departure. The related documents, including a photograph of the beneficiary, are stored in the personal medical files and provided to the healthcare authorities in the destination country.
- ➔ **1.4.5 Manage the flow for the issue of visas and the subsequent steps.** Upon approval of the final list of beneficiaries by the relevant authorities in the country of destination, the consular authorities issue the entry visa, on the basis of Article 25 (EC) No. 810/2009 of 13 July 2009, with limited territorial validity and for the sole purpose of authorising the legal and safe entry of beneficiaries into the country of destination. Copies of the travel documents (e.g.: ETD) are forwarded to the country of destination.

reunification. Registration is also the primary source of information on the persons concerned: who they are and where they are, what their skills/profiles are and what their specific needs are. Registration allows UNHCR, its partners and the governments of transit countries to identify persons in need of special assistance and to respond promptly to their needs.

F 1.2 – Pre-Departure: Implementation Phases

2. PREPARING FOR INTEGRATION: ARRIVAL AND WELCOMING

The following Guidelines apply to:

- Promoters and Members of the HC network (CSOs, sponsors, stakeholders) in EU destination countries.

2.1 APPLICATIONS FOR INTERNATIONAL PROTECTION

- **2.1.1 Support beneficiaries in submitting the applications for international protection upon arrival.** The application for international protection is submitted by each beneficiary to the Border Office at the airport of arrival. Each beneficiary is required to leave fingerprints again. Beneficiaries are supported by the Staff of the Promoter organisations and the Intercultural Mediators in carrying out the operations related to fulfilling the bureaucratic procedures on arrival.
- **2.1.2 Support beneficiaries in completing the process of granting of international protection.** Operators belonging to the sponsoring organisations and the associations of local communities support individual beneficiaries and families in completing the procedures for obtaining international protection. Procedures and time frames can vary according to the legislation in force in the welcoming country⁶. Based on experience, the average time to complete the legal procedure, from recognition of the status to delivery of the residence permit, is 6 months

2.2 WELCOMING

- **2.2.1 Assign the sponsors the task of welcoming the beneficiaries from the moment of their arrival.** Beneficiaries immediately meet the people responsible for their reception at the airport of arrival. Together, they take part in a welcome party. An atmosphere of welcome and friendship is of utmost importance to reduce the refugees' fears and to illustrate the essence of the HCs and related integration pathways. After the celebration, sponsors and beneficiaries go together to the places of reception where the latter will start new life. Beneficiaries are accommodated at local level, in single-family and/or shared apartments. Some refugees – e.g., the most vulnerable – are temporarily accommodated in small welcome centres run by the Promoters or the Sponsors. Individuals, families and small groups can cooperate with the sponsor (and the promoter) in various ways, from the search for (or offering of) suitable accommodation to the provision of goods and assistance in accessing services. The involvement of local networks could evolve into new sponsorships or "co-sponsorships". Guiding criteria in selecting accommodation are based on best satisfying people's needs, which refer to the following conditions: proximity to adequate hospital facilities for people who need medical assistance; proximity to state schools for families with children of school age; capacity to find training and/or employment opportunities, also having regard to previous competencies of the beneficiaries and/or work experience in the countries of

⁶ In the case of Italy, the law provides for hearings at the Territorial Commissions for the Granting of Refugee Status or other forms of protection; the process can last up to 12 months.

origin or elsewhere. The reception system of the Humanitarian Corridors involves grassroots associations, groups of friends, parishes, churches, single families, formal and informal networks of people, etc. A very large number of volunteer operators is actively involved in the different phases and activities of the integration pathway. Cultural mediators support this process throughout its entirety.

- ➔ **2.2.2 Support beneficiaries in the process of granting of ID cards, the certificate of residence and the tax code identification number.** Possessing valid and recognised documents is an important tool for integration, since beneficiaries can feel themselves part of a welcoming community, be aware of their own rights and responsibilities, have a bank account and get regular employment.
- ➔ **2.2.3 Accompany beneficiaries in accessing the National Health system.** Beneficiaries are registered with the National Health system, or in other forms of public healthcare services/insurance. Through the National Health system, beneficiaries can have access to a general practitioner, which is entirely free of charge in some Member States (e.g., in Italy), as well as access to a range of medical tests and the purchase of medicines at reduced prices. Since the bureaucratic procedures and timelines for these services can be complex and lengthy, one of the main tasks of cultural mediators and welcome groups is to accompany beneficiaries in accessing the National Health systems until they are autonomous and fully able to navigate it.
- ➔ **2.2.4 Provide medical care, especially for the sick and most vulnerable.** Forms of assistance not supported by the public healthcare system may be needed, especially for the most vulnerable (e.g. elderly, people with chronic diseases, etc.). Networks of doctors, belonging to the Promoter or activated by the sponsors or co-sponsors at local level, can support vulnerable beneficiaries, with general practitioners and specialists. Vaccinations (especially for children) are among the medical services to be provided to beneficiaries. Psychological support is also a part of medical assistance, since a significant number of beneficiaries can suffer from psychologic disorders: sleep disorders, phobias, etc. The percentage of people with mental health issues or serious disability is quite high among refugees coming from refugee camps or from situations of war.

F 1.3 – Welcoming: Implementation Phases

BOX 3: Intercultural Mediation

GOOD PRACTICE

INTERCULTURAL MEDIATORS

Recourse to cultural mediators is an effective tool supporting a wide range of activities that require a “negotiation” between the beneficiaries of the project and the hosting communities, the operators, the teachers, the doctors, the public officials, etc. This is particularly important in the initial phase of the beneficiaries’ life in the EU country of destination, but it is also important later on, and notably whenever the beneficiaries are dealing with requests for services, obtaining of the documents and granting of refugee status, rights and relationships with the schools, the public officials, etc.

Moreover, cultural mediators give support also when beneficiaries need a clear understanding of laws, habits, social or personal situations, etc. In general, the role of the intercultural mediators is of paramount importance in facilitating the dialogue between beneficiaries and the local communities. This support aims to boost the processes of learning, to speed-up cultural understanding and to avoid or reduce potential conflicts.

Particularly important is the continuity of the work that mediators are called to carry out in the various phases of a humanitarian corridor, from pre-departure in the refugees’ countries of origin to integration pathways in the European host country. In this way, by knowing their history and needs, the mediators are able to actively support the beneficiaries in implementing pathways to autonomy and integration. Very often, the personal stories of the mediators are similar to those of the beneficiaries; this facilitates the establishment of mutual trust, which is always necessary to overcome fears and manage the frustration that can arise from unmet expectations.

3. POST-ARRIVAL AND INTEGRATION

The following Guidelines apply to:

- *Promoters and Members of the HC network (CSOs, sponsors, stakeholders) in EU destination countries.*

3.1 BASIC NEEDS

- ➔ **3.1.1 Provide in-kind and other support to refugees in the initial period upon arrival:** staple goods and services (clothes, food, food vouchers, etc.) are provided to refugees. Public transport cards, mobile phone top-ups and pocket money are also distributed, in order to make refugees capable of managing their own resources and allocating them appropriately to daily needs. The gradual transition from distribution and assistance to independent management of financial resources represents a fundamental step towards the beneficiaries' integration.
- ➔ **3.1.2 Provide guidance to beneficiaries to make them self-sufficient** In the course of project, beneficiaries are accompanied in the achievement of substantial progress from the mere distribution of goods to autonomy. This is a gradual process, which starts once the beneficiaries are familiar with the place where they live. The main points of this process are: a. the ability to navigate independently in the neighbourhoods and the city using public transport; b. the ability to manage money for daily shopping or purchases;

c. the ability to apply for public services and interact with service providers. To this end, the Promoters and Sponsors ensure continuous support to the beneficiaries, which is more intense in the first months upon arrival but decreases over time.

3.2 SOCIAL INCLUSION

→ **3.2.1 Attribute the utmost importance to language learning.** Do not wait for too long, but immediately integrate individuals into courses. The best solution is to include beneficiaries in language classes attended by people from different nationalities and backgrounds. Humanitarian Corridors are not a "closed" scheme (for example, reserved only for students), but open to different groups. For this reason, it is necessary to put people in touch with each other and provide different pathways and levels of learning. Language is the primary means of integration, even for those with low levels of education. It is not enough to provide differentiated learning levels, but it is necessary to tailor the pathways (and, if possible, the syllabuses) for the less educated. Beneficiaries should be enrolled in initial learning courses, from the preparatory level (initial literacy) to level A1 or A2. Selecting language learning centres close to the places where the beneficiaries live is very important to encourage participation. Furthermore, in order to respond to the different needs of beneficiaries, lessons should be scheduled based on flexible days and hours. Some groups of beneficiaries (i.e., those at greater risk of non-integration or social exclusion because of their illiteracy or low education) should have the opportunity to attend courses specifically designed for them. So, the syllabuses corresponding to the lowest learning level (A.1) should be integrated with specific contents, methodology and tools tailored for this target group. The preferred form of language learning is that of courses provided by specialised schools or institutes, but recourse to individual lessons or university language courses is also possible. In addition to language learning, assistance should be provided to some individuals and families of migrants in the procedure of enrolment of their children in state schools. Proper school integration is, in fact, one of the most important elements in the integration process. For the same purpose, school-based support programs for children and minors, provided outside normal school hours, should be considered as a tool to boost learning of the language and, thus, social inclusion of the learners and their families.

BOX 3: Syllabuses for learning of the Italian Language

GOOD PRACTICE

SYLLABUS FOR LEARNING OF THE ITALIAN LANGUAGE

To facilitate language learning, since the 90s the Community of Sant'Egidio has published its own book for the study of the Italian language; a second, improved edition was published in 2023, when Humcore was operational. This book, entitled "L'Italiano per amico" ("Italian as a friend") is based on the modern communication approaches that focus on the integration process of foreigners, through the study of a series of real-life situations that newcomers find themselves facing (for example: going to the doctor, going to municipal offices for

documents, grocery shopping at the market, searching for a job, preparing a curriculum vitae, etc.). Humanitarian Corridors beneficiaries receive the book for free when they arrive at the airport.

For accompanying adult learners with low levels of education in the development of language skills, the Italian Language and Culture Schools of the Community of Sant'Egidio have also launched basic literacy courses. A specific Pre-A1 Syllabus has been published for these learners.

→ **3.2.2 Facilitate beneficiaries' social relationships and their cultural knowledge.**

Sponsors (and Promoters) have the task of promoting socialisation events and accompanying the beneficiaries in establishing positive social relationships with members of the local communities. This is of utmost importance for the beneficiaries, since they need to develop trust in others and the sentiment of belonging to the local community where they live, which are both necessary to achieving a dignified life, self-confidence and autonomy. Knowledge of the national culture and the specific culture of the places where they live is important as well. Cultural orientation and participation in events are the two main tools through which the following topics are addressed: National and European history and habits; standards of living; sociocultural context, population diversity; differences between urban and rural areas; public safety and provision of emergency phone numbers; languages spoken; climatic conditions and geography; health and hygiene; cost of living; media; governance and legal systems; expectations of financial self-sufficiency; the job market and the right to study; citizens' rights and obligations.

→ **3.2.3 Promote and support education of children and young adults.**

Sponsors promote school-based support programs, provided outside school hours. The aim is to speed up learning of the Italian language and fill existing gaps. Afternoon activities often include parties, visits, moments of play, sports, and music, where foreign minors interact with other Italian minors or foreign residents. This kind of support is particularly important for the integration process. It is worthwhile noting that many minors/children never attended school before their arrival in Europe, since in many departure countries access

to the education system is not guaranteed for the children of refugees. The school pathway is also based on cooperation between the schools and the sponsors. The whole education process should then be carefully monitored. This is important for preventing any issues and for favouring beneficial relationships between the young beneficiaries and their class and teachers. For young adults, the program supports the continuation of university studies in the host countries. Collaborations with public and private universities (to be activated by the Promoters and/or the Sponsors) are, thus, very important to this purpose. Sponsors should support beneficiaries in the process of searching for scholarships made available by Centres for Higher Education, Universities or by public / private donors and submitting applications for them.

- **3.2.4 Promote the involvement of the beneficiaries in solidarity or volunteering activities.** Taking care of others can be an important activity for refugees, allowing them to: a. establish relationships with individuals and local communities welcoming them; b. feel useful and activate positive responses to the input received during integration processes; c. gain experience in fulfilling daily tasks and acquire skills and competencies that could prove useful in the workplace. Volunteering can be a great gateway to employment. Voluntary work can be very useful for a person who is looking to develop skills and experience in order to increase their chance of getting a job. It is particularly useful for someone is looking to build up their work experience, confidence and skills at the same time. Volunteers gain work experience, training and the enjoyment of working in their community. They can also often apply for internal vacancies to which they will be better suited because they already have an understanding of the organisation or company.

3.3 WORK INCLUSION

- **3.3.1 Provide orientation, accompaniment and networking.** Promoters and Sponsors (directly or through service providers) offer face-to-face orientation on economic empowerment, such as labour market integration, banking and personal finance. Orientation should be understood as an ongoing process which occurs both formally and informally and which: commences in the immediate post-arrival phase; continues through the refugees' ongoing contacts with employment services, networks and individuals who can help in the process of work inclusion. Refugees are familiarised with the national and local labour markets and assisted in: understanding what employment services are available and how to access them; searching for and applying for jobs; increasing awareness of other opportunities such as volunteering/work placements; reflecting on the benefits of diversity in the workplace; reflecting on implications for cultural misunderstandings/integration challenges in the workplace and exploring how to anticipate/mitigate these challenges. Orientation and assistance encompass the following main topics: job search process; CV writing and application process; how to

prepare for a job interview; clarification and management of expectations; taxation; transferring qualifications; retirement; entrepreneurship. Regardless of the provider, this kind of services should be personalised by taking into account personal and family characteristics of the beneficiary (e.g., level of education). For example, individuals who have spent a large part of their life in refugee camps do not have any experience on life outside the camps and, therefore, on how to manage time, daily work commitments or the job search. On the other hand, others could prefer self-employment rather than employee work. Effective labour market inclusion requires the active collaboration of a variety of actors, including public authorities at local, regional and national level, civil society organisations, economic and social partners and public and private-sector employers. Promoters and Sponsors have the task of concluding agreements or collaboration protocols with: training centres; employment agencies; companies or associations of companies.

- ➔ **3.3.2 Empower skills and provide training opportunities.** Skills and job training is a crucial step in the pathways towards beneficiaries' autonomy. Based on the national and local networks (and by using the services of specialised providers), the Sponsors support beneficiaries in the completion of three main tasks: a. skills assessment; b. fast recognition of qualifications (when possible), and; c. appropriate training for successful labour market integration. The Humanitarian Corridors model encompasses the following main steps of: i. early assessment of the beneficiaries' skills, starting from the pre-departure phase, aimed at identifying strengths and weaknesses with a view to rapid job inclusion in the EU; ii. creation of safe spaces and opportunities for exchange, mutual understanding and trust, mainly through events, celebrations, etc. at local level; iii. breaking down certain gaps and barriers such as information about legal rights, learning appropriate language for work (as a specific, individualised pathway of language training), recognition of skills and qualifications.

- ➔ **3.3.3 Build on the possibility of providing short, work-oriented and personalised training, mentoring and placement pathways, inside or outside the national VET system.** Acquisition of new skills or upskilling is particularly important for individuals with medium to low levels of education. Work-oriented training, especially in sectors and market niches where the greatest job opportunities are available (e.g., depending on the specific country/region, caregiving, food service industry, agriculture, etc.), is therefore of the utmost importance. Getting beneficiaries promptly into work should be a top priority for the Sponsors. Employment fast tracks refugees' integration and their ability to participate fully in society. To start working, refugees and asylum seekers need three things: the right to work, appropriate skills and job opportunities. While resettled refugees have the right to work immediately, those who claim asylum on arrival in the country in which they are seeking protection typically do not. Such is the backlog of asylum cases in many European countries that many asylum seekers are left in limbo for a lengthy period, allowing their skills to rust, depressing their motivation and deterring future employers. Since local work experience is crucial, work placements, internships and apprenticeships are strongly encouraged. That is why Sponsors have the task of guiding the beneficiaries in the process of identifying, selecting (from calls issued by

Public Authorities, partnering networks, companies, associations, etc.) and facilitating the access to apprenticeships work-based learning opportunities for youngsters and adults.

The Story of Anna: from Aleppo to Rome

I am Anna, I come from Aleppo. I think about my city very often. It was beautiful. My husband, Subhi, and I did not want to leave. We resisted until 2016. We had a peaceful life there: family, work, friends, the parish, our dreams were there. We hoped that the war would end, but it only worsened each day. We would leave the house not knowing if we would return. We watched neighbours and friends die. In the last period, bombs fell like rain, all the people were screaming — sirens, the dead, the wounded, destruction everywhere. It was a nightmare. Our little Pamela had just been born, she was a month old, and to save her we decided to leave everything and go.

We went toward Lebanon, but the situation was deteriorating there too. Then there was the port explosion on 4 August 2020. Half of Beirut was destroyed. We too were left without a home again. We could no longer live even in Lebanon.

We started looking. We heard about Humanitarian Corridors. It seemed like a dream: the opportunity to live in peace, serenity, to work and be involved in society, the possibility for Pamela to lead a “normal” life.

When we had the first interview, we finally saw a bit of light. Hope had been rekindled.

We arrived in Italy a few days before Christmas 2020. For us it was truly Christmas, a rebirth for us. Four years had already gone by...

Everything was different: from the time of our arrival. People smiled, they welcomed us with flowers, they were worried about us.

In the following months, we started to discover Rome and Italy, to learn the language. My daughter immediately started school. We never felt alone. Friends of the Community took us by the hand and taught us to walk. They do the most beautiful thing in the world: they give you hope, an essential thing for those who have lived in the darkness of war.

Today, we are at peace. My husband works for a cleaning company and I work with an elderly woman. We live near her. Pamela is happy to study and have friends at school. We thought of returning the gift we have received and so we committed to giving back.

3.4 HOUSING

- **3.4.1 Provide orientation, accompaniment and networking.** Promoters and Sponsors (directly or through service providers) offer face-to-face orientation and accompaniment in access to housing. Access to accommodation is of paramount importance for refugees' integration. In the Humanitarian Corridors model, housing is conceived as a segment of the overall refugee's empowerment process. So, beneficiaries are asked to take responsibility in the process, by actively participating in pathways of housing autonomy encompassing the following main steps: a. knowing how to navigate in the search for housing opportunities: understanding the functioning mechanisms of both the public (requirements and application procedures for social housing) and private (operation of real estate agencies) housing markets; understanding the financial and regulatory tools supporting renting; being able to accurately assess the rental fee. b. knowing how to independently manage the process of renting a property: being able to present oneself and specify one's current housing needs; highlighting one's resources (for example, having experience living in apartment buildings, understanding regulations, having a temporary job that ensures financial stability for a certain number of months of rent, etc.); financial management skills (savings ability); financial independence and therefore the ability to afford the rent; understanding and compliance with apartment building regulations and the rules of communal living; interpersonal skills (to deal with cohabitation situations with other tenants as well as conflicts that may arise with neighbours); ability to maintain the accommodation in order (from activating utilities to taking care of the living space). Accompaniment in access to housing aims to identify sustainable solutions (e.g., affordable rent, social housing initiatives, and other interim solutions), to overcome distrust towards immigrants and to support them in practical tasks linked to housing (such as understanding and signing of rent contracts and related burdens). It includes support for social housing, which mainly involves assistance in finding accommodation, sometimes using housing assistance services or specialised housing cooperatives. Sponsors at local level promote forms of cooperation with local stakeholders (public and private) active in the housing sector, such as: municipalities and cooperatives; property owners and owners' associations; real estate agencies; etc. Shared apartments or co-housing solutions can be considered to facilitate the access to housing, especially for young people or small family groups.
- **3.4.2 Support access to housing through in-kind/not in-kind support decreasing over time.** Promoters and Sponsors act to find forms of temporary support facilitating beneficiaries access to housing. This support may consist of: contributions to payment of rent and utilities; contributions for the purchase of furniture, appliances, maintenance services, etc. In cases where the support consists of a financial contribution, it is granted for a limited period of time, complementarily to other actions envisaged in the integration pathways, and is aimed solely at reducing the initial economic burden on

families, thus boosting the beneficiaries' autonomy and self-sustainability in the long-run.

*The Story of **Ibrahim**: a home for a large family*

Ibrahim arrived in Turin from Syria three years ago with his mother, his six brothers, and his grandfather. His father, who was arbitrarily detained in Lebanon, joined the family a year later. The family arrived in Italy through the Humanitarian Corridors and was welcomed by a group of families who provided support for the initial costs of food and accommodation and accompanied the family every day in their integration process in Turin.

Nine months after his arrival, Ibrahim completed an internship as a pizza maker's assistant. Then, he completed a training course in gastronomy for bars. Finally, Ibrahim got a regular job. He was then provided with housing. Ibrahim and his mother signed a rental contract for a large apartment. The rental fee gradually became affordable for the household. Thanks to the transitional support provided by a group of families in Turin, Ibrahim's brother, Khaled, completed a two-year Vocational Training Course. After the course, he found a stable job that provided the family with an additional income that contributes to the monthly household expenditures.

HUMANITARIAN CORRIDORS:

Active Protocols

Protocols on Humanitarian Corridors

Date	Country of Departure	Country of Arrival	Number of People
15/12/2015	Lebanon	Italy	400
12/01/2017	Ethiopia	Italy	500
14/03/2017	Lebanon	France	500
07/11/2017	Lebanon	Italy	1000
22/11/2017	Lebanon	Belgium	150
03/05/2019	Ethiopia	Italy	600
22/09/2020	Greece	Italy	300
12/04/2021	Lebanon	France	300
27/04/2021	Libya	Italy	500
05/08/2021	Lebanon	Italy	1000
11/11/2021	Iran-Pakistan (Afghans)	Italy	1200
23/12/2021	Libya-Lebanon-Syria- Iran/Pakistan	Belgium	250
/11/2022	Ethiopia	Italy	600
20/12/2023	Libya	Italy	1500

HUMANITARIAN CORRIDORS: *Conclusion*

From a conceptual standpoint, the main achievement of the Humcore project is demonstrating that integration is not simply a phase within the Humanitarian Corridors model, but rather the common denominator across all phases. The process of material integration in the country of new residence is the result of concentric efforts made since the beginning of the process, both through meeting beneficiaries in their countries of origin and through preparing reception networks in Europe. Therefore, the present Guidelines cannot fail to concern the entire Humanitarian Corridors model, and contain indications, suggestions, strategies, and information on all phases of the model, taking into account that the process is entirely unified, and that the progressive steps are not separate: they are carried out according to a uniform and consistent line, based on the fact that the promoters of the Corridors are also the final guarantors of the integration process.

The effectiveness of this model has been demonstrated by its ability to be extended to other contexts and situations. Firstly, the reception structure of the Corridors has been able to accommodate many hundreds of people fleeing the Ukrainian conflict in various European countries. Secondly, the Humanitarian Corridors have served as a model for the opening of a first Labour Corridor between Italy and some African countries, allowing the legal entry of workers needed by the Italian production system, who receive initial professional and linguistic training in their country of origin.

These guidelines are therefore the culmination of a single project, but they can also serve as the starting point for a more aware and operational approach by all stakeholders, both institutional and private, who wish to engage in the dissemination of Humanitarian Corridors at European level, starting from the excellent results achieved in recent years in terms of new arrivals, integration pathways, and upscaling of the model itself as a legal pathway for new categories of people.

The Humanitarian Corridors continue to prove themselves as an effective model, capable of ensuring vulnerable individuals not only full integration but also the respect of fundamental rights recognised as universal by the European Union. The Community of Sant'Egidio and other partners will continue to engage in the dissemination of this model, firmly convinced that it not only meets the urgent needs of the most vulnerable people, but also contributes to the growth and strengthening of the social, economic and human fabric of Europe itself.

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Annex 1: Example of Memorandum of Understanding

MEMORANDUM OF UNDERSTANDING FOR THE IMPLEMENTATION OF THE HUMANITARIAN
CORRIDORS OPENING PROJECT⁷

BETWEEN

[REDACTED]

And

[REDACTED]

⁷ The purpose of this template is simply to provide an example containing only the essential structure and some main provisions. Specific contents will need to be agreed upon between the Promoters and the relevant National Authorities.

Recitals

[This section must be completed with the legal and operational recitals that underlie the signing of the protocol between the signatory parties].

Considering that:

[This section should be completed by including the 'considerations' (nature and experience of the signing parties; nature of the agreement; reference to any preliminary agreements; specific capabilities; etc.)

All of the foregoing recitals and considerations being taken into account,

Signatory Party 1

Signatory Party 2

Signatory Party "n"

AND

Signatory Party 1

Signatory Party 2

Signatory Party "n"

agree to the following:

Article 1

Premise

"The recitals and considerations constitute an integral part of the Memorandum of Understanding for the implementation of the 'Opening of Humanitarian Corridors' project."

Article 2

Purpose

The purpose of the project is to facilitate the legal arrival in [] and under safe conditions of potential beneficiaries of international protection, especially the most vulnerable individuals.

Article 3

Criteria for identifying beneficiaries

Beneficiaries must be identified among those potentially eligible for international protection, in accordance with national and European Union legislation in force on the matter.

In the presence of the condition indicated in the preceding paragraph, the personal and family situations of the applicants will be evaluated with reference to a plurality of preferential criteria:

a) Persons recognized as deserving by UNHCR, at least prima facie, of recognition as refugees under the 1951 Geneva Convention and its 1967 Protocol, or those who are forced to leave their country for well-founded fear of serious harm to themselves;

b) Persons who, although not covered by the previous point a), possess the requirements and present a condition of vulnerability ascertained by [the Promoter1:] and [the Promoter2 to n: _____], consulting the UNHCR for the acquisition of any additional information, which shall be received within a timeframe compatible with the performance of the planned operations, based on personal situation, age and health conditions, and, in any case, in accordance with the criteria expressed in Art. [ref. to national rules on international protection:], as well as Directive 2013/32/EU, on common procedures for recognition and revocation of international protection status.

In a complementary and non-substitutive manner to the previous criteria, admission to the project will take into account the following additional factors, useful for facilitating the identification of integration pathways and excluding or limiting any voluntary secondary movements:
[the following group of rules is additional and not mandatory]

c) Persons who may benefit from support in [] due to the declared willingness of individual subjects, churches, or associations to initially provide them with hospitality and support for a reasonable initial period.

d) Persons who have stable family or social networks in [] and for this reason have declared their intention to settle and integrate into our country.

Article 4

Commitments of the Parties

[Promoters 1, 2, n [redacted]] commit, with their own professional and financial resources, to the activities of identification and thorough evaluation of potential beneficiaries of the project, up to the preparation of individual and family dossiers, in accordance with confidentiality criteria, carried out in transit countries by the proposing organisations, in collaboration with UNHCR regarding persons within its competence. The objective of the evaluation is to identify potential beneficiaries of the international protection system operating in [redacted], as outlined by [ref. to national legislation]. They also commit to taking charge of the transfer to the national territory of those holding an entry visa issued by the competent consular authorities pursuant to Article 25 of Regulation (EC) No 810/2009 of 13 July 2009.

The proposing associations also ensure reception, for a reasonable period of time, and support in the socio-cultural integration process of the beneficiaries, with legal assistance in the phase of requesting international protection from competent national authorities, with measures to strengthen social and cultural integration pathways, also aimed at acquiring linguistic skills and work and social skills, with the aim of promoting the stabilization in [redacted] of the persons included in the project and excluding voluntary secondary movements.

The [insert relevant National Authority] performs a coordinating function for all entities involved in the project. In this context, it informs the territorial commissions [or other bodies as per the relevant national regulations] for the recognition of international protection and the national commission [or other bodies as per the relevant national regulations] about the objectives and operational methods of the present project, with particular reference to the criteria adopted in admitting people to the project and the activity of preparing individual and family dossiers carried out in the initial and preliminary phase before the issuance of entry visas. Additionally, [insert relevant National Authority], following checks in relevant databases and fingerprint examinations, authorises the issuance of visas to the list of beneficiaries compiled by the proposing associations. The [insert relevant National Authority], once the list is approved by the [insert relevant National Authority], commits, within the limits provided by current legislation, to issue entry visas through its diplomatic-consular representations, pursuant to Article 25 of Regulation (EC) No. 810/2009 of 13 July 2009, with Limited Territorial Validity, for the exclusive purpose of allowing legal entry into [redacted] under conditions of personal safety.

Article 5

Countries of Implementation and Implementation Timelines

This project is implemented in [insert the countries of departure], and spans [insert the n°. of] months from the first entry, extendable in case of necessity and upon authorisation from the competent ministries, for a further [insert the n°. of] months. Contacts will be established, or intensified in the case of already initiated relationships, for appropriate coordination with international organisations (UNHCR and IOM), with the relevant public authorities of the countries concerned, with the diplomatic and consular representations of the [redacted] state, and with civil and religious society organisations. In its overall structure, the project may involve a maximum of [insert the n°. of] beneficiaries, roughly over a period of [insert the n°. of] years from the first entry, subject to a possible extension of a further [insert the n°. of] months.

Article 6

Coordination, Monitoring, and Evaluation

The parties establish a coordination, monitoring, and evaluation team for the project, to examine the results achieved, the effectiveness of the operational methods adopted, and the critical issues

identified, in order promptly to make any necessary supplement or potential change to the project itself. This team will also establish the implementation methods of the initiative and address any issues related to individual cases. The team assesses and defines individual situations for which compliance with the criteria outlined in Article 3, paragraph 1, is in doubt. The results achieved at the conclusion of the project will be subject to evaluation, with an initial report after [insert the period] and a final evaluation report, also considering the possibility of any subsequent development of the project.

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